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CONTENTS

Director's Greetings	4
MONGOL EMPIRE STUDIES	
MAY, Timothy Military, Hunting Skills, and Technology	5
MYAGMARJAV, Batsaikhan On Avga Taiji Nobles in Khalkha	23
JOSÉ IVSON, Marques Ferreira de Lima “Born by the Destiny of Heaven”: Gender relations between the Mongols on Secret History of the Mongols (c.XIII)	37
GABRIEL ARRIEL Pedrozo, and PIETRO de Castro Amaral Mongol Empire and the Portuguese Navigations	50
ARCHEOLOGY AND ETHNOLOGY	
BORBALA, Anna Obrusanszky Umay caves and the symbolic rebirth in Eurasia	60
BILGUUN, Erkhemjargal, ERDENEBAT, Ulambayar, and AMARBILEG, Chinbat Unveiling the Journey from Bone to an Item: Exploring bone production and utilization of bone ornaments through Mongol Burials (XIII-XV)	72

Mongol Empire and the Portuguese Navigations

GABRIEL ARRIEL, Pedrozo*
PIETRO, de Castro Amaral**

Abstract

Travels in past historical contexts bring valuable reports. The traveler himself manages to recall, through his reports, a series of aspects that were often unnoticeable for the inhabitants of a place. For Westerners, journeys through Asia are more than mere passers-by and adventurous narratives, they are constructions of imaginaries and images of the other. From a land “beyond” that can be rich, dangerous and vast. That only the only goal is to be explored, discovered, conquered or evangelized in the service of El-rei (a Portuguese term for “the king”). In this work, we seek, through a series of sources, to point out how the Mongol Empire was decisive for the construction of a Portuguese imaginary of the East, a perspective that not only guided Portuguese navigators, but also built a perspective of the world, place and overseas territories.

Keyword

Mongol Empire; Portuguese; Imaginary of the East; Travels; navigators

Introduction

For some historians, the Amboyna massacre, an incident that involved the torture and death of English traders by the Dutch in Indonesia, was one of the first steps towards the fortification of the English India Company, which guaranteed British expansion

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overseas. However, even though some say that Amboyna was a fake,¹ and even though it involved two Portuguese,² Portugal had its “first leap” in maritime expansion in much earlier and gradual manner.

Portugal was born during the Middle Ages, in 1179, with recognition by Pope Alexander III (maximum leader of Christianity at the time) as a kingdom, after the victory of D. Afonso Henriques in a battle against five Muslim kings. And it was precisely in this small Christian kingdom, strategically located in the south of Europe facing the Atlantic Ocean that sailors began to venture into trips beyond Europe towards the African continent in 1385 after resolving several internal conflicts and with the Kingdom of Castile (today Spain). In just over a century, the Portuguese kingdom conquered Ceuta (in the Strait of Gibraltar), and conquered the Cape of Holy Hope (connection between the Atlantic and Indian Oceans). And until the middle of the 16th century, they conquered lands in India (winning asymmetrical battles such as the Battle of the Strait of Hormuz), annexed and colonized (populating) lands in the Americas (today Brazil), established commercial points in Macau in China and in Japan in Nagasaki.

Naturally, in historiography such events had great impacts and resulted in an abundance of government documentary sources and, above all, travel reports. The historiography carried out by travelers who went to the East is very old. The greatest landmark in the West is the reports made by Marco Polo, who was in contact with Kublai Khan, Mongol leader and founder of the Yuan dynasty. The reports of Marco Polo, and other travelers, directed and forged the imaginary. European view of the West³ and inspired European navigators in search of the East.⁴

These interrelations between the Mongol Empire and the expansion of the Portuguese Empire in Asia are the object of analysis in this paper. Through an interdisciplinary approach that combines political, cultural, military and economic aspects, the aim is to demonstrate how the legacy of the Mongol Empire reverberated in the era of Portuguese Discoveries.

The paper seeks to explore not only the historical connections between these two past empires and the formation of the Portuguese imagination about the East.

¹ Games, 2020.

² Chancey, 1998; Games, 2020.

³ Fernández-Armesto, 2001.

⁴ Landström, 1967.

Understanding how Mongol cultural, technological and strategic elements influenced the activities of the Portuguese in Asia is to provide a comprehensive view of the contributions of the Mongol Empire to European expansion, thus enriching the understanding of global history and the relationships between different civilizations of different times.

The imaginary construction

Evidently, the connections between the Western European peoples and the peoples of the Far East Asia can be traced back to antiquity with the Empire of Alexander the Great in 356-323 BC, with contacts and trade routes that went beyond its limits in India. However, cultural and identity elements are key pieces for analyzing projections and constructing imaginaries about others. In this case, the first penetrations of Nestorian Christians into the East are the initial elements for the impact on the minds of Europeans about the East. These are indirect contacts between Western peoples and those from the Far East (China and Mongolia).

Until then, reports of the legendary lost Roman legion, which made an erratic march to China, however, in the 10th century of the Christian Era, Nestorian Christians, a religious current originating in the Byzantine Empire, reached India and Cathay, where they established solid communities of Western faith. However, it was only in the Tang dynasty (618-907), when a prodigious agrarian reform took place in China, with the expropriation of large estates and the opening of hundreds of kilometers of irrigation canals. Since then, there have always been Christian communities in China. During those same years, Jewish communities settled in China, with their innovative commercial transactions. In the year 732, the silkworm, brought from China, was introduced into the Iberian Peninsula, bringing, in addition to the means of silk production, reports and ideas about the distant East with distinct and exotic products and materials.⁵

However, naturally, it was only with the rise of the Mongol Empire that direct contacts between Mongols and their (subservient) subjects with Europeans began. Even though the 13th century is marked as the final period of the Crusades from a local point of view, according to historian Jacques Le Goff, the great global event of that

⁵ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

century was the emergence of the Mongol Empire.⁶

Even though the territorial expansions of the Mongol Empire were felt by Europeans at various points in the trade networks.⁷ It had an impact on his imagination and the construction of the image of the Mongols, territorial conquests on the peripheries of the Western world: Eastern Europe (especially after the battle of Legnica in 1241) and Baghdad (1258).

And it was in this context that two missionaries were sent to the court of Chinggis Khan, one of them the Italian missionary João de Pian de Carpini. It was a reaction movement to the fear of siege by Mongolian troops commanded by Batu, where reports of the attacks and the ills of the war did not go unnoticed by the ears of Pope Innocent IV nor by European leaders and kings.⁸ These are interesting reactions from these men of the past, at the same time that reports of the attacks on Eastern Europe caused fear on the part of the leaders, the fall of Baghdad stirred up the desire to seek an alliance on the part of the Europeans with the Mongols against the Muslims, whom they seek to expel from the Holy Land (Levante) in several crusades.

In effect, the collective memory of Europeans in relation to the Mongols resembles the times of Attila, whose figure aroused a mixture of fear and fascination for the Byzantines. The Mongols' reputation as formidable warriors and their merciless siege tactics on cities left an indelible mark on the European psyche of the time, as was the case with the Council of Lyon, which mentioned the Mongols.⁹ Faced with this dilemma, many Western leaders redoubled their efforts to protect their borders (especially those closest to Eastern Europe). Fortifications were erected and defensive strategies meticulously planned in an attempt to contain the imminent threat of the Mongols. The constant pressure exerted by this external threat shaped not only military strategies, but also the politics and social organization of these regions. The words of missionary João Caprini from the East were that the Mongol Empire should embrace Christianity, as the Great Khan could conquer the world.¹⁰ And this did not go unnoticed.

On the other hand, European princes who aimed to conquer the Middle East

⁶ Le Goff, 1988.

⁷ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

⁸ Vicente, 2004.

⁹ Vicente, 2004.

¹⁰ Phillips, 1971.

adopted a different approach. Recognizing the power of the Mongols and seeing possible advantages in an alliance, they planned to establish diplomatic contacts. These alliances often aimed at specific objectives, such as territorial expansion or strengthening local political power, in an intricate game of interests.

Thus, the influence of the Mongols in Eastern Europe and the Middle East was not just restricted to battles and conquests, but permeated the political strategies and social dynamics of the time, leaving a lasting legacy in the history of these regions.

However, the sending of missionaries was not a success. The peace sought by Pope Innocent IV through the conversion of Güyük Khan to Christianity (in 1242), or even the diplomatic forays of Louis IX of France seeking answers from Mangu (Möngke) Khan did not result in anything concrete.

It was in this context that the legend of Prester John, a mythical Christian legendary king who ruled lands in the East, gained space in Marco Polo's narrative. In which he had conflicts with Chinggis Khan and resulted in an intense battle: "There were great losses, on both sides, but in the end Genghis Khan won this battle, in which Prestes João died."¹¹

When Marco Polo "kills" the mythical character, he exposes the weakness of Christians (represented by the legendary icon of the defense of Christians against Muslims) suffering against the Mongols. And this death has an impact on the imagination of the time, since the emergence of myth is a mental correspondence with reality. Myth is one of the forms of human consciousness,¹² "*the examination of myths illuminates the structure of this consciousness.*"¹³ Its effervescence shows an attitude, its acceptance points towards the collective longing, the embodiment of the fabulous in the form of the imaginary, distant and unattainable kingdom. Its physical inexistence alleviated the wear and tear of the concrete characters, perhaps that is why "its mythical content and its long duration"¹⁴ collapsed with what Marco Polo envisioned: The Great Mongol Empire.

It was not just fear and the threat of invasion that resulted from this exchange. Naturally, we also hear about goods and commerce, especially the Silk Road, which also reached the European imagination at the time, revealing a rich East full of

¹¹ Polo, 1985: 95.

¹² Eliade, 2019.

¹³ Mora, 1982: 266.

¹⁴ Franco Jr., 1994.

spices. These medieval stories and the almost uninterrupted flow of goods shaped the collective imagination in the West, and among them was Portugal, which until then had not taken a decisive position, given that it was at the height of military activities against Muslims in the Iberian Peninsula, but he carefully absorbed the movements of history. Marco Polo's writings and his figure would remain in the European imagination throughout the centuries and continue to the present. In the same way as the legendary figure of Prestes João.

The influences of trade routes and the Mongol Empire on the Portuguese

The commercial routes between East and West, over the centuries, were the main access routes between both cultural centers. They were subject to all sorts of changes, especially under the influence of climatic conditions that resulted in large population movements, the emergence of empires, political alliances and conflicts. These, among other elements, modified its lines and borders.¹⁵

The term 'Silk Road' is used to refer to a broad framework of commercial, cultural, and religious exchange between the Western world and the Far East. The Silk Road was extremely important not only for the East but also for the West. European countries benefited from the flow of goods. These materialities of the East have always been the target of attention on the part of Westerners, going back to the origins of the West, the Roman Empire, which during the period of the Late Republic invested attacks against the territory dominated by the Parthians, an ancient people whose territory was strongly coveted in view of who through their trade routes introduced exotic goods to the Roman market. They dominated a space between the West and the East, whatever the routes, whether by land or sea, they would pass through their domains.¹⁶

Still in the Roman period, several eastern merchants were extensively present in Rome according to historians of the time, possibly they were "intermediaries" on this long journey, and not people from the Far East.¹⁷ During the Middle Ages, these commercial routes had an important presence of Jews, who were well established in

¹⁵ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

¹⁶ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

¹⁷ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

China,¹⁸ between the years 1270-1273, as reported by Jacob de Ancona, author of the book *A Cidade da Luz* (2001) a Jewish merchant who was before Marco Polo. However, it was not long before this commercial web was subject to a gradual process of expansion of Muslim rule.

And this entire commercial chain was once again subject to the geopolitical relations of the time, now with Chinggis Khan. In one of his acts as a ruler the city of Samarkand was razed, however, it didn't take long to be rebuilt since it was a very strategic point for the commercial flow of goods between the West and East. During Mongol rule, contact with the western side intensified, in addition to expanding its domains to the shores of Europe. Decades later, Chinggis Khan's grandson, Kublai, managed to unify China, providing greater stability for trade.¹⁹ What caused the Franciscans to create missions in China, in which a Portuguese man was present, Friar Lourenço de Portugal, who had also gone to the East as ambassador of Pope Innocent IV, in diplomatic activities with Tatar peoples and, especially, the great Khan of the Mongols, the first recorded contact of a Portuguese person with the Mongols.

In addition to the goods themselves that found their way to Europe, an imaginary was created in the minds of Portuguese and other Europeans about a rich and prosperous East and the idea of "seeking riches" in the East became more and more a place in the mind. than in the physical world. This impacted the first Portuguese navigations in search of the "East Indies", which Columbus tried to find his way to by sailing West instead of East. Interestingly, even though it was already in the Renaissance, this impact of medieval imagery, which we mentioned above, still prevailed, such as the example of Afonso de Paiva, sent by the Portuguese king D. João II, to investigate the mythical kingdom of Prestes João, now in Africa, in an attempt to make him an ally in a possible expedition to India. Afonso de Paiva dies, but Pêro da Covilhã's reports allowed her to learn much of the story in his book *Verdadeira Informação das Terras do Preste João das Indias*.²⁰

In the century. XV, through strategic aspects and technological advances intensely subsidized by the monarchs, such as the establishment of nautical schools, resulted in generations of great Portuguese navigators. A great milestone was the caravel, an extremely agile and versatile ship, which, combined with an extensive knowledge of astronomy, calculations of latitudes and longitudes, made it possible not only to reach

¹⁸ Siqueira de Carvalho, 2002.

¹⁹ de Abreu Freire, 2022.

²⁰ Cortesão, 1940; Sousa, 2005.

India in 1498, but also in China in 1513 and Japan in 1543.²¹

The Portuguese navigations opened a new route, a sea route that bypassed the powers then established between the West and East, initiating a new facet in the history of the planet. The Portuguese were aware of the land empires that intersperse these commercial routes, and they knew the riches of the East, to reach them they launched into the sea.²²

This entire effort to reach the East was based on solid information about the wealth that arrived in places like Italy, France and the Iberian countries. In addition to the products themselves, the cultural exchange that occurred with travelers and writings that roamed the silk route was something significant that aroused the curiosity of the "exotic" in the minds of Europeans. Portugal as a foreign empire, once in Asia in the 19th century. XVI it takes advantage of several existing structures in Southeast Asia built and left as a legacy by the Mongols. The globalized economy that the Portuguese built with their navigation across extreme distances was only possible due to the structures and arrangements of empires prior to their arrival.²³

Conclusion

The Mongol Empire was something remarkable for its time, crossing its borders and influencing not only the imagination of a people like the Portuguese, but its history. It is a key piece for understanding what the French historians of the Annales School called Total History (*Histoire Totale* in French), a holistic and general understanding, which aims to overcome the superficiality of political and individual events, exploring different aspects of a historical context. When we analyze these influences of the Mongols, it becomes clear that the transformations introduced by the empire were not limited to their time, but have continued to this day, influencing the ways in which cultures and societies interact and develop throughout the historical contingency of the Mongols centuries.

By expanding their empire across vast regions of Eurasia, Chinggis Khan's successors gave rise to an incipient process, which resembles globalization. Commercial routes, with emphasis on the so-called Silk Road, promoted the exchange

²¹ Barros, 1975.

²² de Abreu Freire, 2022.

²³ Albuquerque, 1989.

of goods, ideas and technologies between the West and East, laying the foundations of a globalized economy that would develop over the following centuries, such as its undeniable influence in the case of Portuguese, which had sought precisely to circumvent the limitations that it had. This movement of goods plays a fundamental role in the formation of the modern world.

Through this reflection, we hope to expose how understanding the Mongol Empire is important for understanding the relationships between societies that had little direct contact. These past societies cannot be analyzed and understood as mere isolated chapters, but continuous links in an extensive historical chain. This in-depth understanding allows us to contextualize subsequent events and developments. Therefore, the study of the Mongol legacy is more than an academic exercise; It is an essential tool for deciphering its complexities and its impact on later historical periods, such as during Portuguese navigations in the 16th century and the consolidation of the Portuguese Overseas Empire with its domains in Asia.

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